

International Organizations and United Nations: Peace Activities

Htay Htay Win*

Introduction

An international organization is an institution created by agreement among two or more states across borders for the conduct of political, economic and other functional interactions. International organization did not appear until the 19th century. The twentieth century is more or less an age of international cooperation.

An international organization is a formal arrangement of states to facilitate cooperation among member nations in security, economic and social fields. Modern international organizations are of two basic types, the public variety known as intergovernmental organizations (IGOs) and the private variety, the international non-governmental organizations (INGOs). IGO is opposed to a non-governmental organization (NGO). International organizations bodies set up by the multilateral agreement among states, and it is rather different from transnational organizations or NGOs, such as International Red Cross, ASEAN University Network, and Green Peace etc. For most example of the former would the League of Nations and the United Nations. Currently international organizations such as UN, ASEAN, WTO, IMF and EU play very important role in determining relations among states.

The theory of international organization has evolved from developments in such areas as internationalism, transnationalism, complex interdependence, the study of regimes, functionalism, federalism and integration. The central focus of all these concerns is an attempt to get beyond the political, social and economic fragmentation. However, the phenomenon of international organization also raises a number of important of questions. For example, what factors and forces help to explain the emergence of international organizations? and why are international organizations created? This paper explains that emergence and nature of international originations and how and why has the UN's approach to peace activities and peacekeeping evolved.

Rise of International Organization

The earliest embryonic international organizations were created after the Napoleonic Wars. These include the Congress of Vienna (1814-15), which established the Concert of Europe which continued until WWI. The number and membership of such organizations gradually increased during the 19th and 20th centuries, in of them being existence in 1914. By 1929 and the onset of the world economic crisis, their number had reached an inter-war peak of 83. The end of WWII marked a new boom, with the number of international organization soaring to 123 by 1949, with new organizations including the United Nations. This reflected not only an awareness of growing interdependencies amongst states, linked to concerns over power politics, economic crises, human rights violations, developmental disparities and environmental degradation, but also the emerging hegemonic role of the USA, which saw the pursuit of US national interests and the promotion of international cooperation as mutually sustaining goals.

Although their number subsequently declined, largely due to the dissolution of Soviet bloc organizations at the end of the Cold War, this masks a substantial growth in international agencies and the institutions, as the number bodies spawned by international organizations themselves has continued to grow. By the mid 1980s, the total number of international organizations had reached 378, with the average membership per organization standing at over 40 compared with 18.6 in 1945 and 22.7 in 1964.

*Dr., Lecturer, Department of International Relations, Dagon University

International organizations are characterized by rules that seek to regulate the relations amongst member states and by a formal structure that implements and enforces these rules. International organization not only provides a means of cooperative action but also multiple channels of communications which on varying levels overlie traditional diplomatic structures.

The most important of all international organizations, the United Nations (UN), has a constitution that have embodied in a Charter, ratified in 1945. International organizations have generally been established in order to accomplish all or some of the following purposes.

- Regulation of international relations primarily through techniques of peaceful settlement of dispute among nation-states.
- Minimizing or at the least, control of international conflict and war.
- Promotion of cooperation, developmental activities among nation-states for the social and economic benefit of certain regions or of humankind in general.
- Collective defence of a group of nation-states against external threat.

The Common characteristics of international organizations include: a permanent organization to carry on a set of functions, voluntary membership of eligible parties, a basic instrument stating goals, structures, and methods of operation— a broadly representative consultative conference organ and a permanent secretariat to carry on continuous administrative, research and information function.

As instrument, their members to secure specific ends are using international organizations. In other words, they became the instruments for the promotion of particular foreign policy objectives. International organizations can be viewed as arenas forums within which member states meet to debate policy. It enables particular state as groups of states to bring issues to international attention and to attempt to change prevailing attitude. An international organization can perform the role of international actor if it can take independent decisions and is not significantly affected by outside forces. Thus international organizations can affect international relation in a variety of ways. As instrument and arena, they provide states with an additional resource base. As actor, organization can develop independent personalities and produce unintended consequences for states.

The rise of IO is sometimes seen as evidence of the emergence of a global governance system. Global governance is wider and more extensive phenomenon of informal as well as formal processes and a wider array of actors.

Why are International Organizations Created?

The political debate reflects disagreements between liberals, realist and other about, amongst other things, whether the impulse to create international organizations stems from the collective interests of states generally. Realist views on international organizations are ineffective, weak and undesirable. If world politics is shaped by a struggle for power rather than a harmony of interests, there is little scope for the levels of cooperation and trust. They tend to erode the authority of the nation stated because of their implications for sovereignty.

Liberal view on international organizations are a reflection of the extent of interdependence in the global system an acknowledgement by states that they can often achieve more by working together than by working separately. Neoliberal view on international organizations are while not rejecting the concern about “relative gains”, they hold that states may be more concerned about making “absolute gains”, the scope for cooperation at an international level is considerable. The effectiveness of international organizations is closely linked to the emergence of a global hegemony.

There is a further range of debates about the motivations processes through which integration and institution building at an international level has been brought about. Three main theories have been advanced: Federalism, Functionalism and Neofunctionalism. Federalism refers to territorial distribution of power through which sovereignty is shared between central (national or international) bodies and peripheral ones. The Federalist perspective, international organizations are a product of conscious decision-making by the political elites. The problem of war is caused by sovereign states pursuing self-interest in a context of anarchy, peace will only be achieved if states transfer at least a measure of their sovereignty to a higher, federal body.

Functionalism views the formation of international organizations as an incremental process with a growing range of government functions performed more effectively through collective action than by individual states. Integration is largely determined by recognition of growing interdependence in economic and other areas. Neofunctionalism, which sought to explain and deepen through a process of spillover. These theories, institution building have largely been developed a means of explaining the process of regional integration, e.g., European integration.

From the League to the United Nations

The League of Nations had been founded at the Paris Peace Conference of 1919 with the aims to enable collective security, to arbitrate over international disputes and to bring about disarmament. It was inspired by US President Woodrow Wilson's Fourteen Points, established as the basis for long-term peace in post WWI Europe. Collective Security is the idea or practice of common defense, in which a number of states pledge themselves to defend each other, based on the principle of "all for one and one for all". The League, nevertheless, suffered from major defects, e.g., lack of joining major states and effective power, only making recommendations, not binding resolutions and no mechanism for taking military or economic action against miscreant states. The UN established in 1945 through the San Francisco Conference (April - June 1945), having a membership of 193 states. The key goals of both organizations were the promotion of international security and the peaceful settlement of disputes.

The early origins of the UN emerged during WWII itself with an alliance of 26 states. The UN officially came into existence on 24 October, 1945 since known as UN Day. The UN sprawling and complex organization and at the heart, it is a hybrid body, configured around competing concerns: the need to accept the realities of great power politics and to acknowledge the sovereign equality of member states. This has created two UNs, one reflected in the Security Council, the other in the UNGA.

The Security Council is the most significant UN body. It is responsible for the maintenance of international peace and security. It serves as negotiator, observer, peacekeeper and, ultimately, peace enforcer. It has the power to pass legally-binding resolutions, to suspend or expel members, to impose economic sanctions and to take military action to maintain or restore peace and security. It has 15 members. It is dominated by the P-5, its permanent veto powers– the US, Russia, China, the UK and France. The other 10 members are non-permanent members elected for two years by the UNGA.

The general Assembly (Parliament of nations) is a deliberative body that represents all members of the UN equally. Each member has a single vote. It can debate and pass resolutions on any matter covered by the Charter. It has a specific responsibility to examine and members' contributions, and elect, in conjunction with Security Council, the UN Secretary General and the judges of the International Court of Justice. Important decisions must be carried by a two-

thirds majority, but, crucially, these decisions are recommendations rather than enforceable international law. It neither has a legislative role nor does it oversee or scrutinize, in any meaningful sense, the Security Council or the Secretariat.

Promoting Peace and Security

The principle aim to the UN is to maintain international peace and security. The responsibility is vested in the Security Council. The performance of the UN can be judged in terms of the extent to which it has saved humankind from deadly military conflict. The point that WWII does not follow the two World Wars shows a supreme achievement of the UN. Realists have argued that the absence of global war since 1945 has had little to do with the UN, being more a consequence of the “balance of terror”.

Without UN, an unanswerable question is that how global and regional conflict would have developed and whether ‘cold war’ would have become ‘hot’ ones. Evidently, the UN has only had limited and intermittent success in establishing a system of collective security that can displace a reliance on violent self-help. The capacity of the UN to enforce a system of collective security is severely limited by the fact that it is essentially a creature of its members. For much of its history, the UN was virtually paralyzed by superpower rivalry. During the Cold War, on most issues, two blocks’ opposing positions prevented the Security Council from taking decisive actions. The use by the P-5 of their veto powers resulted clashes between them and resistance amongst them has prevented the UN from developing its own military capacity. During much of the Cold War, the UN was characterized by deadlock and paralysis.

The end of the Cold War was the beginning of a new chapter for the UN. A new era of UN activism appeared to be a major component of “new world order.” Since 1990, the Security Council has approved non-military enforcement measures, usually linked to peacekeeping operations, have become much more common. However, early hopes for a UN dominated new world order were quickly disappointed because of some high-profile peacekeeping failures (e.g., USA’s invasion of Iraq in 2003).

During the post– Cold War period, the UN has been forced to confront a range of new problems and conflicts: the reluctance of states, seeming to be unipolar world order and the emergence of the P-1 in the Iraq War. The international political focus has itself shifted. The UN’s role used to be to keep the peace in a world dominated by conflict between communism and capitalism. Now, it is forced to find a new role in a world structured by the dynamics of global capitalism.

Global capitalism bears conflict increasingly arising from imbalances in the distribution of wealth and resources. The UN’s role in promoting peace and security has been conflated with the task of ensuring economic and social development, the two being merged in the shift from traditional peacekeeping to ‘multidimensional’ or ‘robust’ peacekeeping. Peacekeeping means a technique designed to preserve the peace when fighting has been halted, and to assist in implementing agreements achieved by the peacemakers.

From Peacekeeping to Peace-building

Peacekeeping falls somewhere between the UN’s commitment to resolve disputes peacefully through means such as negotiation and mediation and more forceful actions to maintain security. Between 1948 and 2009, the UN carried out by 63 peacekeeping operations. In 2009, 16 of them remained active, involving 80,000 troops, almost 11000 uniformed police and about 2,300 military observers, drawn from 117 countries. These were supported by about 6,000 international civilian personnel, 13,000 local civilian personnel and over 2,000 volunteer workers. During 2008-09 the budget for UN peacekeeping operation was about \$7.1 billion.

Traditional or classical or 'first generation' UN peacekeeping amounts to monitoring and observing the peace process in post-conflict situations, with peacekeepers being deployed after a ceasefire has been negotiated and with no expectation of fighting except in the case of self-defense. This form of peacekeeping is consensual and requires the consent of the host state, its advantage being that the ability to report impartially on adherence to a ceasefire builds trust between previously warring states or groups.

In a context of East–West rivalry, a strict reliance on neutrality and impartiality, monitoring post-conflict situations rather than influencing them, appears to be the only way in which the UN could contribute to the maintenance of peace. However, that approach became increasingly unsustainable in the post-cold war period, especially as the number of UN peacekeeping operations increased significantly. Importantly, the task of peacekeeping became more complex and difficult due to the changing nature of violent conflict. As interstate war became less frequent and civil war became more common, more conflicts were entangled with ethnic and cultural rivalries and endemic socio-economic divisions.

This nature was reflected in two developments from the 1990s onwards. First, as peacekeeping's were increasingly being dispatched to conflict zones in which violence remained an ongoing threat, if not a reality, there was greater emphasis on 'robust' peacekeeping, sometimes portrayed as 'peace enforcement'. 'Peace enforcement' means coercive measures, including the use of military force, used to restore peace and security in situations where acts of aggression have taken place.

Second, as conflict situations became more complex, there was recognition, over time, that the design and focus of peacekeeping operations had to keep up. This led to the advent of 'multi-dimensional' peacekeeping. 'Multi-dimensional' peacekeeping are, which includes, in addition to implementing a comprehensive peace agreement, the use of force to achieve humanitarian ends, the provision of emergency relief and steps towards political reconstruction. The emphasis therefore shifted from peacekeeping to peace-building. Peace-building is a long process of creating the necessary conditions for sustainable peace by addressing the deep-rooted, structural causes of violent conflict in a comprehensive manner. Strictly speaking, peace-building is a phase in the peace process that occurs after peacemaking and peacekeeping have been completed. However, these activities invariably overlap to a greater or lesser degree, meaning that peace-building resembles what is often called 'multidimensional' peacekeeping. Peace-building as long-term conflict resolution involves a wide range of strategies, economic, political and social as well as military. These includes the following: economic reconstruction, repairing or improving the economic and social infrastructure, de-mining, the demobilization and retraining of former combatants, the reintegration of displaced peoples, establishing community organizations, and revising governmental arrangements or 'state-building.'

Does UN Peacekeeping Work?

How successful has multidimensional peacekeeping in the post-Cold War period been? UN peacekeeping has been effective and cost-effective. UN had succeeded in keeping the peace and promoting democracy. However, there have been a number of peacekeeping failures, notably in Rwanda, Somalia and Bosnia. UN peacekeepers were little more than spectators during the genocides slaughter in Rwanda in 1994. UN-backed US intervention in Somalia led to humiliation and withdrawal in 1995, with warlord conflict continuing unabated. Some have seen such events as evidence of the pitfalls of intervention in alien places lacking civil order and legitimate political institutions. Failings on the ground have included the lack of a clear mission, and especially serious gaps between the mandate for intervention and the security challenges confronting peacekeepers, the varying quality of peacekeeping forces and a

confused chain of command, and a general reliance on ‘deterrence by presence’, reelected in a reluctance to use force on the face of peace-breakers who use force freely and criminally. Failings a higher level has been associated with a lack of political will, and conflicting priorities and agenda, in the Security Council and amongst other member states.

However, there is also evidence that the UN has learned lessons. Ever since 1992, there has been an acknowledgement that peacekeeping alone is not enough to ensure lasting peace. The growing emphasis on peace-building reflects a desire to identify and support structures tending to strengthen and solidify peace to avoid a relapse into conflict, helping to establish positive peace. Although the military remains the backbone of most peacekeeping operations, the many faces of peacekeeping now include administrators and economists, police officers and legal experts, deminers and electoral observers, and human rights monitors and specialists in civil affairs and governance.

The UN Peace building Commission was established as an advisory subsidiary body of the UNGA and the Security Council founded in 2005, to support peace efforts in countries emerging from conflict, by bringing together all relevant actors (including international donors, the financial institutions, national governments and troop-contributing countries), marshalling resources, and advising on and proposing integrated strategies for post-conflict peace building and recovery.

The peace building Commission can accomplishment through the Commission’s own efforts because of being advisory, absolute classical peacekeeping within the UN peace-building, difficult peace enforcement and possibility only under specific conditions. However, peace building is a holistic exercise that straddles the UN ‘harder’ and ‘softer’ sides, its concern with promoting peace and security fusing with its commitment to economic and social development.

The UN Charter committed the organization to promoting ‘social progress and better standards of life’ .The architects of the UN recognized the interconnected of economic and social issues. It is an awareness of the links between the economic turmoil of the Great Depression and the rise of political extremism and the growth of international conflict. In its early phase, these issues were extended little beyond post-war reconstruction and recovery, particularly in Western Europe and Japan. However, from the 1960s, a major shift in favor of the promotion of economic and social development was evident due to three factors:

- 1) the process of decolonization and the growing influence of developing states within the ever- expanding UN focused more attention on the unequal distribution of wealth worldwide. The North-South divide thus the rival the significance of East-West rivalry within the UN.
- 2) a great awareness of interdependence and the impact of globalization from the 1980s onwards meant that there was both an increased acceptance that economic and social problems in one part of poverty and inequality are linked to the structure of the global economy.
- 3) as acknowledged by the transition from peacekeeping to peace- building, the rise of civil war and ethnic strife underlined that peace and security, on the one hand, and development, justice and human rights o the other, are not separate agendas.

The UN’s economic and social responsibilities are discharged by a sprawling, and, seemingly, ever-enlarging array of programmes, funds and specialized agencies, supposedly coordinated by ‘the Economic and Social Council’. Its mains areas are human rights, development and poverty reduction and the environment. The principal vehicle for global development policy is the UN Development Programme (UNDP), created in 1965. UNDP has

a presence in some 166 countries, working with them on their own solutions to global and national development challenges and helping developing countries attract and use aid effectively. By focusing on the notions of 'human development' and 'human security', the UNDP has also fostered innovation about poverty and deprivation, moving away from a narrowly economic gap.

However, by the late 1990s, concerns about deepening global inequality, and especially the plight of sub-Saharan Africa, produced growing anxiety about the impact of the UN's development programmes. The 1990 human development Report, for example, noted that while the top fifth of the world's people richest countries enjoyed 82 percent of the expanding export trade, the fifth enjoyed barely more than 1 percent (UNDP 1999). The desire to rate the UN's Development Programme led to the unveiling in 2000 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). These set a target for, among other things, halving extreme poverty, halting the spread of HIV/AIDS and providing universal primary education. The UN's 2009 annual report on the achievement of the MDGs concluded that overall programme been too slowly for most of the targets to be met by 2015, particularly in global economic and food crises. Despite frustrations and difficulties, it is nevertheless clear that the UN has done more than any other organization creating the state to alleviate the economic and social problems of developing countries.

A further issue is that the security challenges facing the modern UN are vastly different from those in earlier decades. Amongst other things, these include threat of nuclear terrorism, the problem of state collapse and the disruption caused by the spread of infectious diseases. The changing nature of war and armed conflict raises particular difficulties for the UN in its peacekeeping and g peace-building roles. Not only do the rise of identity wars and the links between civil strife, humanitarian and refugee crises and endemic crime make sustainable peace difficult to achieve, but they also strain the relationship between the quest for global justice and respect for state sovereignty. The UN, in addition, faces a continuing problem of who will foot the bill for its activities. While UN peacekeeping, development and other activities remorselessly, to expand, major donor states have become more reluctant to keep up with their financial contribution, partly using these as levers to influence policy within the organization.

In the light of these challenges, the issue of UN reform has become increasingly prominent. In the late 1990s, the then Secretary-General, Kofi Annan, embarked on an overarching reform programme which aimed to improve the coordination of the UN's economic and social arrangements and to strengthen the norms of the multilateral system.

However, most would argue the process remains incomplete and needs to be applied to a much broader range of UN activities. However, other important areas of reform are in peace open development and human rights. The 2000 Brahimi Report on Peace made a major contribution to reviewing UN peace operations, and provided the backdrop for the creation of the UN Peace building Commission in 2005. In relations to human rights, the UN has been highly successful in creating a detailed body of international human rights legislation, and also in producing bodies that can observe and authoritatively report on adherence to global human rights norms.

Conclusion

International organizations are created out of a composite of factors. These include the existence of interdependencies among states which encourage policy-maker to believe that international cooperation can serve common interests and the presence of a hegemonic power willing and able to bear the costs of creating, and sustaining, an international organization. The

UN is the only truly global organization ever constructed. The UN is nevertheless a hybrid body, configured around the competing need to accept the realities of great power politics and to acknowledge the sovereign equality of member states. The principal aim of the UN is to maintain international peace and security, with responsibility for this being vested in the Security Council. However, then has been restricted in carrying out this role particularly by the veto powers of the P-5 and the lack of an independent military capacity. The UN's mixed performance in the area of peacekeeping has led to an increasing emphasis instead on the process of peace-building.

The UN's economic and social responsibilities are discharged by a sprawling, and seemingly, ever-enlarging array of programmes, funds and specialized agencies. Its main areas are human rights, development and poverty reduction, and the environment. Such widening concerns have ensured strong support for the UN, particularly across the developing world. The UN faces a range of important challenges and pressures for reform. These include those generated by the changing location of global power in an increasingly multipolar world, those associated with criticisms of the composition and powers of the Security Council, and those related to the UN's finances and organization.

Highly-publicized peacekeeping 'failures' have distorted the image of the UN's effectiveness in keeping the peace. The UN peacekeeping operations are more often successful than unsuccessful. At an operational level, there are clearly functions that the UN is better at performing than any other body, including small-scale peacekeeping and peace activities, the provision of humanitarian aid and the monitoring of elections. The shift towards multidimensional peacekeeping has also been beneficial. The world is not peace without UN, thus the UN is still the world leading organization in the present era.

References

- Andrew Haywood, (2011), *Global Politics*, Palgrave Foundations, Macmillan Press, UK.
- Armstrong, D., Lloyd, L. and Redmond, J., (2004), *An Introduction to the History of Modern International Organization that places a Particular Emphasis on the Development of the UN*, International Organization in World Politics.
- Graham Evans and Jeffrey Newnham, (1997), *The Penguin Dictionary of International Relations*, Swansea.
- Kelly-Kate, S. (2003) *PEASE International Organizations, Perspectives on Governance in Twenty First Century*, Prentice Hall, New Jersey, USA.
- Rittberger, R. and Zangl, B., (2006), *International organization: Polity, Politics and Policies, Systematic Theoretical and Empirical Introduction to the Evolution, Structure and Policies of International Organizations*.
- Robert Garner, Peter Ferdinand, and Stephanie Lawson, (2012), *Introduction to Politics*, Oxford University Press.
- Thakur, R., (2006), *The United Nations Peace and Security: From Collective Security to the Protect*, An analysis of the UN's Role in Maintaining Peace and Security that examines the Developing Framework for its Peacekeeping Operations.
- UNDP, (2008), *Basic Facts about the United Nations*, UNDP, Yangon.
- Weiss, T.G., (2009), *What's Wrong with the United Nations (and How to Fix it)*, A Stimulating Examination of the UN's Alleged Ills and of Possible Cures.

Online Resources

www.un.org

www.un.org/news

www.un.org/wcm/content/site/chronicle

unyearbook.un.org